

Integrated designs for future floating offshore wind farm technology – Towards nature inclusive innovations

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ABSTRACT: This paper shows that through a comprehensive interplay between engineering design, modelling, analysis and optimisation, fundamental nature inclusive design innovations for the floating offshore wind industry can be provided. With the increased use of the marine space for energy production, environmental impacts move into focus when developing innovations for offshore wind. However, the ambitious capacity goals potentially compromise the goal to protect and preserve bio-diversity in sea basins. Hence, the offshore wind industry is faced with the challenge to balance human needs for clean energy with nature's and society's demands of decreased negative environmental and social impact. Nature inclusive designs can contribute to this challenge; however, their concept is largely under-explored.

1 INTRODUCTION

Offshore wind, with a global cumulative capacity of approx. 60 GW in 2022 (DOE 2023), is undoubtedly one of the main contributions to the green energy transition. Considering, for instance, the targets formulated in the Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan of the European Union (60 GW by 2023 and 300 GW by 2050), this trend will likely continue and be fostered by new technology developments within the industry. Moving further offshore to locations with abundant higher wind speeds and increased wind resource calls for new technologies to allow cost-efficient harnessing of the wind energy at deep water depths (Soares-Ramos et al. 2020). While bottom fixed structures, such as monopiles or jackets, are established for water depths < 50 m, floating concepts are becoming cost-efficient for water depths > 50 m (Sørensen and Larsen 2021).

Among the current concepts of floating offshore wind, tension leg platform (TLP)-type systems are promising due to their small footprint, higher resistance to severe environmental loading, and low mass, hence cost (Freeman et al. 2016). Figure 1 shows the current design concept of the TLP-type floating offshore wind turbine (FOWT) developed by GICON[®]. Consisting of a gravity based anchor with attached tendons and a four-legged floating substructure, these systems allow a so-called one-step installation, where the entire system (gravity anchor, substructure, turbine) can be towed to the installation site and then deployed by ballasting the anchor (Vanjakula et al. 2022). This simplifies, for instance, known challenges during the transport and installation (T&I) of TLP-type systems (Freeman et al. 2016).

Despite their potential, FOWTs are at an early stage of their development and large commercially operating wind farms are yet to be deployed. Amongst others, the higher environmental loads on the foundations and structures at deep water depths, as well as the additional complexity of the entire system (e.g., mooring, dynamics, operation and maintenance (O&M)), are reasons for the lacking technology commercialisation in floating offshore wind. While techno-economic optimisation is one of the main motivators for innovation and a push towards commercialisation of floating offshore wind technologies, positive environmental impact of marine installations is recently moving into focus (Degraer et al. 2020).

In general, a reduced use of primary raw materials fosters leaner designs of marine installation and follows efforts towards resource-efficient and sustainable engineering. More specifically, the floating offshore wind industry can leverage the fact that installations are immersed in a biologically rich environment. This environment, on the one hand, demands protection and conservation, and on the other hand sometimes is in need of restoration after decades of degrading from industrial exploitation. To that end, nature

Figure 1: Artist's impression of GICON[®]'s tension leg platform (TLP)-type FOWT concept (courtesy of GICON[®])

inclusive design (NID) innovations show significant potential for environmental compensation by means of, e.g., providing habitats for species. Knowledge of NID for floating offshore wind applications, however, is lacking (see Section 2) and challenges arise regarding, for instance, the effect of NIDs on structural engineering (loads, dynamics, etc.), O&M activities, or the levelised cost of energy (LCOE).

The Horizon Europe INF⁴INiTY project (Integrated designs for future floating offshore wind farm technology) (INF⁴INiTY 2024) tackles these challenges by developing NID innovations of sub-sea components of floating offshore wind systems. In particular, the project aims to develop: (1) an innovative NID for gravity anchors and their associated scour protection system and (2) an innovative primary artificial reef structure combined with the floating substructure of a FOWT. This paper presents an overview of the INF⁴INiTY project; it aims to accomplish the following items:

- To present the state-of-the-art and knowledge gaps of nature inclusive designs for floating offshore wind installation
- To lay out the INF⁴INiTY methodology, which will be followed to provide the technology innovations
- To present the pertinent future work, enabling the development of the INF⁴INiTY innovations

2 NATURE INCLUSIVE DESIGN

According to Hermans et al. (2020), NIDs refer to designs with which habitats for (native) species are being created through the integration or addition of specific features. Thereby, NIDs compensate for and/or restore degraded or reduced natural habitats. In their study, the authors define three specific types of NIDs for (fixed-bottom) offshore wind, namely add-on options, optimised scour protection, and/or optimised cable protection. Identifying examples for those three categories (which are later extended by Cale and Churn (2021)), the authors build up a comprehensive catalogue of NIDs for offshore wind. Furthermore, Hermans et al. (2020) postulate an example design methodology, which should be followed in order to ensure ecological functionality and minimal uncertainty concerning NID implementation.

2.1 *Examples of NID*

Following the definition of Hermans et al. (2020), Cale and Churn (2021) investigate the feasibility of NID for (fixed-bottom) offshore wind in the Irish Sea. In order to assess options, the authors pose specific questions to be answered prior to the development of the NID. Those concern the specific target species or communities, the temporal and spatial scale of the project, the natural environmental conditions, the substrate for the NID (artificial or natural), and, finally, the cost and budget of the project.

With the answers to those questions, the ideal NID options can be selected. However, the authors also mention numerous challenges during the development of NIDs, ranging from lacking legislative guidance, over questions concerning decommissioning, to the introduction of non-native and invasive species. Similarly, Marin-Diaz et al. (2021) state that NIDs for offshore wind (scour protection, sub-sea structures etc.) are species-targeted, meaning that specific selection of NID features depend on the locality and the target species that will benefit from the design.

Examples of NIDs in offshore and coastal engineering can be found in the literature by means of climbing aids for lobster populations on offshore structure (Buck et al. 2017), eco-friendly scour protection (Lengkeek et al. 2017), or intertidal foreshore stabilization using seadomes (Marin-Diaz et al. 2021).

2.2 *Artificial reefs*

A specific and, in some applications, established form of NID is the implementation of artificial reefs. According to Pan et al. (2022), artificial reefs are structures, intentionally deployed in the water to improve the ecological environment. Specifically, artificial reef structures provide an environment for organisms to prey, avoid enemies, gather, reproduce, and grow. Thereby, this definition closely follows the

more general definition of NID by Hermans et al. (2020).

The first artificial reef in Europe was installed in Monaco in the 1960s for nature conservation purposes (Jensen 2002). Since then, research has been conducted, analysing marine benthic community dynamics and structure or evaluating novel designs and construction materials for artificial reefs (Lima et al. 2019). However, most of the research is focused on sit-bottom type artificial reefs (Pan et al. 2022) either by means of dedicated structures (such as seadomes (Marin-Diaz et al. 2021) or Reefballs® (Cale and Churn 2021)) or by means of other structure (oil rigs, shipwrecks, etc.). The former are referred to as primary artificial reefs, while the latter are referred to as secondary artificial reefs (Lima et al. 2019).

More recently, with the increased installation of (fixed-bottom) offshore wind turbines, the surface piercing support structures (monopiles or jackets) are largely considered as artificial reef structures (Krone 2012). Degraer et al. (2020) provide a comprehensive overview of the effects of (fixed bottom) “offshore wind farm artificial reefs” on the ecosystem structure and functioning. For instance, the authors highlight studies which found a 4000-fold increase in biomass around the turbine footprint, compared to the status-quo, prior to installation. This increase in biomass (and biodiversity) is mainly focused around the hard vertical substrate of the pile/jacket and potentially more horizontal habitats by means of the foundation and scour protection. With respect to the succession of species, the authors highlight that the vertical substrate will be dominated by a few species, which may be non-indigenous for instance in the splash zone, which forms an entirely new habitat, compared to the previous undisturbed ocean surface. Similarly, the rough surface of the scour protection may attract non-indigenous species, which previously were not found on, e.g. soft sediment grounds. Thus, both desired and undesired effects of offshore wind installations as artificial reefs can be identified, which in turn calls for an in-depth knowledge of the impacts of such installations on the eco-systems and vice versa.

To that end, field studies on abundance of, e.g., the Atlantic cod (Werner et al. 2024) or European lobster (Thatcher et al. 2023) were performed recently. Generally, higher abundance of species is found in the proximity of the (fixed-bottom) offshore wind installation with.

While some research is available for fixed artificial reefs, very little work has been done towards floating installations and reefs. In their overview, Degraer et al. (2020) mention the specific difference between fixed-bottom and floating offshore wind that, e.g., monopiles spread the entire water column, providing a “connection” between the different vertical zones and habitats, while this is not the case for floating structures.

Pan et al. (2022) mentioned standalone float-

ing Fish Aggregating Devices to support fishery in their review of structure types and new development prospects of artificial reefs in China. The authors point out the challenges with respect to the hydrodynamic characteristics of floating reefs, compared to their sit-bottom counterpart, due to the inherent coupling of the dynamics of all required sub-systems. Perkol-Finkel et al. (2008) study the spatial and temporal patterns of benthic communities on floating and fixed artificial habitats. Here, “classical structures” such as buoys and rafts are considered and the authors’ field study is based on primitive reef structures, omitting the floating offshore wind case. Finally, very recently, Luo et al. (2022) showed the opportunities for floating artificial reefs based on a concept design. While only staying on a concept level, the authors highlight specific key advantages of floating reefs, namely no disruption of soft seabed, possible deployment in the photic zone of deep water environments, flexible and fast deployment, multi-use of the mooring system, e.g., for extreme load mitigation or energy production.

3 INF⁴INiTY PROJECT

Based on the reviewed literature on NIDs, it can be observed that the concept of nature inclusiveness is, to a certain degree, established and benefits are being acknowledged; however, further research is generally required (Svane and Petersen 2001, Hermans et al. 2020, Cale and Churn 2021). In particular, in the floating offshore wind industry, no applications or concepts are available to date. In the INF⁴INiTY project, an interdisciplinary and multi-sectoral consortium of 13 European partners, aims to provide two major NID innovations for the floating offshore wind industry (see Section 3.1), following an elaborate methodology, embracing data sourcing, modelling and analysis, optimisation, and validation (see Section 3.2).

3.1 Innovations

3.1.1 Gravity anchor and scour protection

Spanning over areas in the order of $\mathcal{O}(45 \times 45 \text{ m}^2)$ with penetration depths in the order of $\mathcal{O}(1 \text{ m})$, gravity anchors are a significant disturbance to the prevailing environment at and around the deployment site. The additional spread of the scour protection ($\mathcal{O}(100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2)$) extends this disturbance, ultimately rendering the installation (anchor and scour protection) a significant stressor to the ecosystem.

For the application of NID in scour protection, three basic options are available: (i) Additional rock layer; (ii) Adapted grading armour layer; and (iii) Placing independent units on/in the scour protection layer (Cale and Churn 2021). Among these options, adding additional rock layers is straightforward; however, it may not be preferable, because of the additional thickness added to the scour protection layer,

thereby increasing cost and complexity. Placing independent units on/in the scour protection layer shows potential for shear stress amplification. The self- and on-bottom stability of these units are of additional concern. Furthermore, it should be kept in mind that these units would introduce additional production, installation, inspection, and monitoring costs.

Finally, adapting the grading armour layer is an option for NID in scour protection, which will be followed in the INF⁴INiTY project (see Figure 2). In particular, a general concept design for the scour protection with an adapted grading armour is proposed, which combines traditional scour protection designs with NID without introducing alien structures. Given the fact that NIDs are species specific, concept designs need to be refined based on the installation site. To that end, three different case studies for different example sites (Scottish Sea, Baltic Sea, Adriatic Sea, see Section 3.2) are considered, for which specific designs are developed.

Figure 2: Schematic concept of the proposed NID for the gravity anchor and scour protection system.

3.1.2 Floating structure and artificial reef

In contrast to the gravity anchor, where NIDs provide compensation of disrupted ecosystems, NIDs for the floating structures show significant potential to provide entirely new habitats for target species by means of including artificial reef structures (see Section 2). Thus, it is proposed to integrate primary artificial reef structures in GICON[®]'s floating offshore wind design, thereby providing new habitats for species (see Figure 3). As for the gravity anchor and scour protection system, a general concept design of the artificial reef structure will be developed. The general design will provide the boundary conditions regarding dimensions, weight, overall shape, etc. These boundaries will be determined in close connection with the engineering design of the floating structure in terms of loading conditions and system dynamics (e.g., natural frequency). Based on the case studies as used for the gravity anchor innovation, specific designs of the artificial reef for three examples sites are developed. Here, for instance, the specific shape (crevices, porosity, etc.) and surface characteristics (roughness, ma-

terial, etc.) are being determined based on the target species at the site, with the aim of avoiding settling of invasive species.

Idealised artificial reef structure

Figure 3: Schematic concept of the proposed artificial reef structure for the floating substructure.

3.2 Methodology

In order to provide the proposed NID innovations for the floating offshore wind industry, a methodology is proposed which embraces the aspects of modelling and analysis (composed of numerical simulation, experimental testing, and Front End Engineering design (FEED)) in concert with optimisation and technology validation. All this is accompanied by sourcing required data to provide boundary condition (e.g. environmental loads) and supporting decision-making. The interlinks between the methodology aspects are shown in Figure 4.

3.2.1 Study sites

The three regions, Scottish Sea, Baltic Sea, and Adriatic Sea, are all suitable locations for floating offshore wind deployment; however, feature different characteristics. Table 1 provides a summary of the characteristics. Maps of bathymetric features of the three different study sites can be seen in Figure 5.

Table 1: Region specific environmental conditions

	Scottish Sea	Baltic Sea	Adriatic Sea
Wave climate	Strong	Moderate	Mild
Wind climate	Strong	Strong	Mild
Soil conditions	Sand, gravel, mud	Clay, sand	Clay, mud, silt, sand

The Scottish Sea extends over an area of approx. 460 km² and covers parts of the Atlantic Ocean and the North Sea. At the inshore regions of the Scottish coastline (within Scottish territorial waters) particularly the east and south-east regions have the lowest water depths of up to 60 m compared to the northern part where water depths vary up to 100 m. Further offshore (outside the Scottish territorial waters), regions in the west coast of Scotland have the highest water depths > 100 m (Marine Scotland 2019). The seabed

in Scottish waters is highly varied, with areas of hard, rocky substrate, sand, gravel and mud, while sand and gravel sediments are prevalent throughout Scottish waters (Marine Scotland 2019). The common benthic habitats across the Scottish water include circalittoral sands, mixed sediment, and biogenic reef communities. The subtidal sediments support communities of biogenic reefs, mussel beds, burrowing worms, crustaceans and bivalve molluscs. Within Scottish waters, deep sea habitats are found almost exclusively to the west and north of Scotland and include cold water coral reefs, coral carbonate mounds, submarine canyons, sea mounts and deep-sea sediments. These habitats in deep sea support a considerable biomass and are considered to be the largest ecosystem on earth (Webb 2010). The wind conditions in the areas of North and West Scotland are rated IEC wind class of I (> 10 m s⁻¹) and II (up to 8.5 m s⁻¹) within Scottish territorial waters. Annual significant wave heights range from approx. 1 m up to 3 m, which is considered a strong wave climate.

The Baltic Sea is characterised by a stratification of the water column. In the upper layer, brackish/fresh water from rivers lay on lower water with higher salt concentration. Water with higher salt concentration flows into the Baltic Sea under storm conditions from the North Sea/Kattegat and into the Baltic Sea, passing through the inner Danish waters. The sea-bed is typical sand at lower depth and mud/hard clay in deeper waters (> 50 m). There are areas with relatively low water depth, but the main basins have water depths typical larger than 50 m (see Figure 5). The Baltic Sea is vulnerable towards negative environmental impacts. For instance, the cod is highly dependent on the salt concentration, as recruitment of Baltic cod critically depends on egg survival (Köster et al. 2001). Hydrographic conditions in the central and eastern Baltic are critical for successful cod reproduction and the inflow of saline and oxygenated water from the North Sea (Busch et al. 2024). The wind energy content at Bornholm Basin is IEC class II but close to I. The wave conditions are mild (annual significant wave heights range from approx. 0.5 m to 1.5 m) compared to for instance the North Sea.

The Adriatic Sea is a semi-enclosed basin laying between the Italian and Balkan Peninsula. It is connected to the Mediterranean Sea via the Ionian Sea at the South. With an average depth of 260 m, the Adriatic can be attributed as a shallow sea basin. A variety of sediment characteristics can be seen in the Adriatic seabed, ranging from clay and mud to silt and sand (Amorosi et al. 2016). As opposed to the Scottish and Baltic Sea, seismicity in the Adriatic Sea is categorized as Zone 2 with mixed shallow crustal fault and deep subduction zones (Sumer 2014). Therefore, earthquake-induced liquefaction is a potential threat that should be addressed for offshore wind developments to be located in the Adriatic. The hydrography of the region is characterized by water inflow from the

Figure 4: The INF⁴INiTY methodology (Figure adapted from INF4INiTY 2024).

Eastern Mediterranean and fresh water run-off from Italian rivers, which produce both seasonal latitudinal and longitudinal gradients in hydrographic characteristics along the basin (Buljan 1979). As a result, a rich biological diversity and population is seen in the Adriatic fauna. The Adriatic Sea has a moderate wind climate, with an IEC wind class rating of II–III. The wave conditions are mild, with annual significant wave heights range from approx. 0.5 m to 1.0 m, reaching up to extremes as has as 6 m.

3.2.2 Front end engineering design

Based on initial designs for a gravity anchor, scour protection system, and the floating substructure (see Figure 1), FEED is performed for the NIDs and their integration in GICON[®]'s FOWT design. Challenges arises to comply with the established design criteria (load capacity, system dynamics, T&I, construction cost, manufacturability, etc.) while adapting the design towards nature inclusiveness, thus providing the envisaged innovations. Data from experimental and numerical modelling, as well as boundary conditions from the accompanying data sourcing (uncertainties in metocean conditions, requirements for commercialisation, etc.) and optimisation are being used as input to the FEED. Additional requirements specific to the NID are being sourced and defined in the framework of the project. It is well known that NIDs are location and target species specific, thus, first general designs are being proposed and then refined based on the environmental loading and biological conditions for three different case study sites (see Section 3.2.1).

3.2.3 Numerical modelling

To provide required input data and boundary conditions, numerical modelling is an integral part of the development of the NID innovations (see Figure 4). The employed modelling canvas is split into geo-/morphodynamic analysis, hydrodynamic analysis, and aerodynamics/wind farm modelling.

In terms of numerical geo-/morphodynamic analysis, focus is put on scour (and sinking) of, as well as liquefaction (wave- and seismic-induced) around marine structure. To that end, the recently developed, OpenFOAM[®]-based, finite-volume liquefaction toolbox by Shanmugasundaram et al. (2022) will be employed and extended towards scour.

For the hydrodynamic numerical modelling, OpenFOAM[®], the smoothed-particle hydrodynamics solver DualSPHysics, as well as the recently developed fast optimisation tool MOST (Sirigu et al. 2022) are used. While OpenFOAM[®] will be primarily used for the analysis of the wave-structure-interaction (WSI) of the floating substructure and artificial reef in operational conditions, DualSPHysics is used to carry out simulations of the WSI under extreme conditions. In both models, the effect of the artificial reef with the marine growth is considered through a porous media approach and the turbine is only considered via a lumped mass. MOST circumvents the latter model simplification by calculating the aerodynamic forces by using the blade element momentum theory and look-up tables for fast computation. The hydrodynamics are implemented in MOST via WEC-Sim (NREL 2022).

Finally, aerodynamic and wind farm modelling is conducted in order to optimise farm layouts and provide power performance estimates. For that, three models are exercised. The in-house computational fluid dynamics code EllipSys3D (Sørensen 1995), the aeroelastic code HAWC2 (Larsen et al. 2013), and a stochastic reduced order model (ROM). Coupling EllipSys3D with the aero-elastic code HAWC2, which contains a built-in model of the floater and mooring system, enables the description of the fully coupled wind and wave forcing and response of floating wind turbines consistently throughout large wind farms. With inputs from this modelling chain, a ROM is then able to provide flow and farm performance characteristics at low computational cost.

3.2.4 Experimental modelling

In concert with the numerical modelling, experimental modelling is performed to provide crucial design inputs to the FEED. Also, the experimental modelling tasks can be split into geo-/morphodynamic analysis and hydrodynamic analysis. For the former, geotechnical characterisation in advanced monotonic and cyclic triaxial tests is carried out, as well as morphodynamic studies for the experimental performance analysis of the gravity anchor and scour protection system. For instance, a physical modelling campaign will be undertaken in a wave-current flume, where models of generic subsea structures with dif-

Figure 5: Depth maps of the three study sites: a) Adriatic Sea, b) Baltic Sea, c) Scottish Sea.

ferent weights and sizes will be investigated. Additionally, different foundation types will be tested to acquire knowledge on anchor stability for the three site-specific soil conditions.

Concerning the hydrodynamic analysis, a multi-scale approach is followed. Medium scale experiments are carried out in a wave-current flume in order to provide parametrised validation and calibration data for the implementation of the artificial reef and marine growth in the numerical models. Furthermore, medium scale test of the floating substructure with artificial reef parametrisation are conducted in the coastal and ocean basin of Gent University. At large scale, the entire FOWT, including gravity anchor, scour protection system, and floating substructure with artificial reef parametrisation is studied to perform technology validation.

3.2.5 Techno-environomics optimisation

Holistic optimisation considering technical, economic and socio-environmental aspects of the floating offshore wind farm is essential to provide robust and cost-efficient NIDs. To that end, multi-level and multi-objective optimisation is performed (see Figure 6), articulating key criteria for all relevant aspects: (i) technical with structural integrity, hydrodynamic and geotechnical performance, as well as T&I and O&M feasibility; (ii) economics by considering detailed installation, capital and operational expenditure, as well as externalities synthesized in an enhanced LCOE; and (iii) socio-environmental by means of impact analysis.

4 CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

The Horizon Europe INF⁴INiTY project aims to support finding a balance between clean energy generation and decreased negative environmental and social impact by providing integrated NIDs for the floating offshore wind industry. This paper provides an overview of the project's methodology and target innovations. The following conclusions can be drawn:

Figure 6: Schematic framework of the holistic techno-environomic optimization

(1) While NID concepts are, to some degree, established for fixed installations, the development and analysis of NIDs is largely under-explored for floating offshore wind. With the prospect of a drastically increased number of FOWTs in the fragile marine environment calls for a push of NIDs towards application on a commercial scale.

(2) INF⁴INiTY promises truly innovative NIDs for the gravity anchor and scour protection system, as well as the floating substructure based on GICON[®]'s FOWT design. This is enabled through a comprehensive methodology using state-of-the-art (and beyond) techniques and infrastructure. However, the multitude of influencing factors and the complexity of the marine environment renders this tasks challenging and careful execution of the tasks is paramount.

4.1 Future work

Being at the beginning of the research work within the INF⁴INiTY project, future work along the entire methodology path can be identified. The most immediate future work concerns: (1) The definition of design load cases for the target sites; (2) Defini-

tion and design of the medium-scale experimental test campaign and model setup; (3) Initial development of the hydrodynamic and aerodynamic model setups; (4) Geotechnical soil characterisation of soil samples from the target site.

Being immersed in a wider program of the European Commission to develop critical technologies for the offshore wind farm of the future (HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-05), INF⁴INiTY will connect with projects of the same call (TAILWIND, FLOAT-FARM, MADE4WIND) to maximise impact and exploit synergies.

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